

Building the Legal Knowledge Graph for Smart Compliance Services in Multilingual Europe

D5.8 Evaluation Report of the Lynx platform and pilots

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ACRONYMS LIST

BPMN	Business Process Model and Notation
RDF	Resource Description Framework
SHACL	Shapes Constraint Language
GUI	Graphical User Interface

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In D5.4 “Testing and evaluation plan” [1] we described our plan for testing that the Lynx system with its pilots addresses the requirements of the Lynx project. With this deliverable, D5.8 “Evaluation Report of the Lynx platform and pilots”, we present the application of the methods described in D5.4, the obtained results, and the conclusions that have been drawn.

Section 2, “Integration level testing and evaluation”, reports the updated versions of the integration tests for the Lynx platform presented in the “Integration level testing and evaluation plan” Section of D5.4, shows the results which have been obtained from their application and the conclusions that have been drawn.

Section 3, “Pilot use cases level testing and evaluation”, shows the results of the tests and benchmarks that have been performed to verify the conformance of the three Lynx pilot applications with respect to their requirements. The testing methodology for the Lynx pilot applications has been presented in the “Pilot use cases level testing and evaluation plan” Section of D5.4.

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1 INTRODUCTION

In D5.4 “Testing and evaluation plan” we have described our plan for testing that the Lynx system with its pilots addresses the requirements of the Lynx project. With this deliverable, D5.8 “Evaluation Report of the Lynx platform and pilots”, we present the application of the methods described in D5.4, the obtained results, and the conclusions that have been drawn.

This document is organized in two sections:

- Integration level testing and evaluation, in this section will be presented the tests whose goal is verifying the functionalities of the Lynx platform supported by many Lynx microservices integrated together.
- Pilot use cases level testing and evaluation, in this section will be presented the tests whose goal is verifying the Lynx pilot applications with respect to their requirements.

2 INTEGRATION LEVEL TESTING AND EVALUATION

D5.4 described the plan for the Lynx platform integration tests. The presented tests have been subject to internal discussion in the months after the publication of the deliverable, and some changes to the initial plan have been made:

- The test scenario for “Test 1: Private collections” has changed and now considers the access to collections only through the `https://apis.lynx-project.eu/document-platforms/{documentPlatformId}/collections/{collectionId}/*` pattern. This is justified by the following changes in the Lynx API:
 - Indexes and collections have become independent REST resources.
 - The access to the population workflow API is now restricted to developers and trusted third party clients.

The new version of the test scenario for “Test 1: Private collections” is reported in Section 2.1.1.

- “Test 2: population workflow” has been divided into two separate tests:
 - The first test takes the same name of the original one, but the purpose has changed to only verifying the correct functioning of the population workflow using different input combinations. This test along with its new test scenario is described in Section 2.2.
 - The second test, which we have named “Test 3: large document ingestion”, describes a scenario for measuring how fast the system is able to ingest documents. This test together with its new test scenario is described in Section 2.3.

This section then reports the updated version of the integration test plan, shows the results which have been obtained from their application and the conclusions that have been drawn.

2.1 TEST 1: PRIVATE COLLECTIONS

A Lynx collection is identified and accessible through the following URL pattern:

`https://apis.lynx-project.eu/document-platforms/{documentPlatformId}/collections/{collectionId}/*`

Here “*” denotes a possible URL compliant suffix which identifies some collection sub resource, for instance “/documents” and “/top-k-documents”.

Lynx private collections are collections whose access requires an access token and is governed by access policies. Some examples of possible access policies are “Only user xxxx”, “Only client yyyy” and “All Lynx users”. All the Lynx collections with the following URL pattern are private:

`https://apis.lynx-project.eu/document-platforms/ldp/collections/{collectionId}/*`

Lynx public collections are collections whose access does not require an access token. All the Lynx collections with the following URL pattern are public:

`https://apis.lynx-project.eu/document-platforms/upm-elastic/collections/{collectionId}/*`

The two objectives of this test are:

- Verifying the confidentiality of private collections, which means that private collections should be accessible only by the clients and users for which the evaluation of access policies is positive.

- Verifying that public collections are accessible without an access token.

2.1.1 Test scenario

The test scenario consists of the following steps:

1. Choose a public collection and check that it is accessible without providing an access token.
2. Create a private collection and assign to it some access policies.
3. Retrieve an access token representing the identity of user/client authorized to access the collection created in step 1.
4. Try to access the test collection using the token in step 2 and verify that the system correctly accepts the request.
5. Retrieve an access token representing the identity of some unauthorized user/client.
6. Try to access the test collection using the token in step 4 and verify that the system correctly denies the access.

2.1.2 Test application and results

Following the steps described in Section 2.1.1:

1. The *covid* public collection can be retrieved without providing an access token:


```

{"total":129,"docs":[{"@context":"http://lynx-project.eu/doc/jsonld/lynxdocument.json","id":"BOA-d-2020-90072","type":["lkg:Legislation","nif:Context","lkg:LynxDocument"],"text":"I\nEl pasado 11 de marzo de 2020, la Organización Mundial de la Salud elevó la situación de ocasionada por el COVID-19 a pandemia internacional. La rapidez en la evolución de los hechos, a escala nacional e internacional, requiere la adopción de eficaces para hacer frente a esta coyuntura. Las circunstancias extraordinarias que concurren constituyen, sin duda, una crisis sanitaria sin precedentes por el muy elevado número de ciudadanos afectados como por el extraordinario riesgo para sus derechos.\nTras esta declaración, el Departamento de Sanidad aprobó, con fechas 13 y 14 de marzo dos órdenes por las que se adoptan medidas preventivas y recomendaciones de salud pública en la Comunidad Autónoma de evolución del COVID-19. Posteriormente, el Gobierno de España ha declarado el estado de alarma mediante Real Decreto 463/2020, de 14 de marzo, para la ge crisis sanitaria ocasionada por el COVID-19, desarrollado profusamente en los días posteriores con objeto de concretar las medidas adoptadas, coordinar l Administraciones públicas y garantizar su eficacia.\nLa ejecución de las medidas adoptadas produce un profundo impacto sobre el funcionamiento de todas l como ha ocurrido en el caso del sector público autonómico, se ha concretado en la identificación de los servicios de carácter esencial para actuar frente se concretó en la Resolución de la Dirección General de la Función Pública y Calidad de los Servicios de 16 de marzo de 2020, de nuevas medidas de contin de la Comunidad Autónoma de Aragón en relación al COVID-19 motivada por la declaración del estado de alarma por Real Decreto 463/2020, de 14 de marzo. So
    
```

2. The collection *private-collection-test* is created and the “Only *cuatrecasas* client” policy is assigned to it:

Only "cuatrecasas" Client Can Access "private-collection-test" Collection

Name * Only "cuatrecasas" client can access "private-collection-test" collection

Description

Apply to Resource Type OFF

Resources *

Apply Policy

Name	Description	Actions
Only cuatrecasas client		Remove

Decision Strategy

3. An access token for *cuatrecasas* client is retrieved using the OAuth2 client credentials flow.

4. A *GET* <https://apis.lynx-project.eu/document-platforms/ldp/collections/private-collection-test/documents> request is performed, the system correctly authorizes and serves the request:

The screenshot shows a REST client interface with the following details:

- Method:** GET
- URL:** `{{baseUrl}}/collections/:collectionId/documents?sort=asc&iimit=10&offset=0`
- Authorization:** OAuth 2.0. Access Token is `eyJhbGciOiJIUzUzI1NiIsInR5cCI6IkpXLT...`. Header Prefix is `Bearer`.
- Configure New Token:** Token Name is `token 2`, Grant Type is `Client Credentials`, Access Token URL is `https://keycloak-secure-88-staging.cloud.itandtel.at/auth/realms/Lynx/pr...`, and Client ID is `cuatrecasas`.
- Body:** Status: 200 OK, Time: 3.07 s, Size: 557.47 KB. The response is a JSON object:


```

1 {
2   "total": 1,
3   "docs": [
4     {
5       "@context": "http://lynx-project.eu/doc/jsonld/lynxdocument.json",
6       "id": "ldp/collections/private-collection-test/documents/123",
            
```

5. An access token for a generic user is retrieved using the OAuth2 code flow.
6. A *GET* <https://apis.lynx-project.eu/document-platforms/ldp/collections/private-collection-test/documents> request is performed using token from step 4, the system correctly denies the access returning a 403 error code:

The screenshot shows a REST client interface with the following details:

- Method:** GET
- URL:** `{{baseUrl}}/collections/:collectionId/documents?sort=asc&iimit=10&offset=0`
- Authorization:** OAuth 2.0. Grant Type is `Authorization Code`. Callback URL is `https://oauth.pstmn.io/v1/callback`. `Authorize using browser` is checked. Auth URL is `https://keycloak-secure-88-staging.cloud.itandtel.at/auth/realms/Lynx/pr...`, Access Token URL is `https://keycloak-secure-88-staging.cloud.itandtel.at/auth/realms/Lynx/pr...`, and Client ID is `Postman`.
- Body:** Status: 403 Forbidden, Time: 335 ms, Size: 146 B.

2.1.3 Conclusions

The system behaved as expected, so the test can be considered passed.

2.2 TEST 2: POPULATION WORKFLOW

The objective of this test is to check the correct functioning of the population workflow using different input combinations. In other words, this test is designed to verify that all the instances of the population workflow behave as specified in the Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN) model, whose final

version is described in the “Population workflow” Section of D4.5 “Final implementation and report of Data and Content Curation Services” [2].

2.2.1 Test scenario

The test scenario consists of trying to start new instances of the population workflow with different input combinations and verifying that the system behaves as follows:

- If the input document is invalid with respect to the Lynx Shapes Constraint Language (SHACL) shapes¹, then the system should respond with an error without starting any instance.
- Otherwise, the system should create a new population workflow instance with the provided configuration parameters. Then, when the execution of the started instance is completed, the following conditions should be verified:
 - If one of the model identifiers serving as input does not exist in the corresponding service, or if the specified collection or index does not exist, then the population workflow instance should have produced a business error.
 - Otherwise, the enriched document should be retrievable from the specified collection and searchable using the specified index.

This test procedure should be performed with both valid inputs and non-valid inputs. In particular, the main input that should be tested and the respective expected outcomes are described in Table 1.

Document	Collection	Index	Enrichment Configuration	Expected outcome
Valid	Existing	Existing	At least one model is provided, and all the specified models exist	A new instance is created. When the instance is completed, the enriched document should be retrievable from the specified collection and searchable using the specified index.
Invalid	Existing	Existing	At least one model is provided, and all the specified models exist	The system responds with an error which describe what rule of the data model has been violated. No instance should be created.
Valid	Not existing	Existing	At least one model is provided, and all the specified models exist	The system should start a new instance which should end with a “not existing collection” business error.

¹ The Lynx SHACL shapes can be used to verify that a RDF document is compliant with the rules of the Lynx data model (<https://lynx-project.eu/doc/lkg.owl>)

Valid	Existing	Not existing	At least one model is provided, and all the specified models exist	The system should start a new instance which should end with a “not existing index” business error.
Valid	Existing	Existing	At least one model is provided, and at least one of the specified models does not exist	The system should start a new instance which should end with a “not existing enrichment model” business error.

Table 1 Input combinations and expected outcomes that should be verified in Test 2: Population workflow

2.2.2 Test application and results

We start with an input which should not generate any error (first row of Table 1):

1. The new collection *test-d58* is created
2. The new index *test-d58* is created
3. A new population workflow instance is started using a valid Lynx document, the *collectionId* and *indexId* of step 1 and 2, and a valid enrichment configuration:

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	documentPlatform	ldp
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	collectionId	test-d58
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	indexId	test-d58
<input type="checkbox"/>	entityLinkingProjectId	nisi repr
<input type="checkbox"/>	enTranslationModelId	nisi repr
<input type="checkbox"/>	esTranslationModelId	nisi repr
<input type="checkbox"/>	neTranslationModelId	nisi repr
<input type="checkbox"/>	deTranslationModelId	nisi repr
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NERModelId	ner-wikinerEn_LOC;ner-wikinerEn_ORG;ner-wikiner...
<input type="checkbox"/>	GEOModelId	nisi repr
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TimExModelId	model-en
<input type="checkbox"/>	SummModelId	nisi repr
<input type="checkbox"/>	priority	0
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	tag	my tag

4. When the execution of the instance created in step 1 is completed, the document can be retrieved from collection *test-d58*, and searched using index *test-d58*:

The screenshot displays two REST client requests and their corresponding responses.

Request 1 (GET): The URL is `{{baseUrl}}/collections/{collectionId}/documents/{documentId}`. The request is configured with Path Variables: `collectionId` (value: `test-d58`) and `documentId` (value: `test-doc`). The response status is 200 OK, with a time of 1541 ms and a size of 142.58 KB. The response body is a JSON object:

```

1 {
2   "@context": "http://lynx-project.eu/doc/jsonld/lynxdocument.json",
3   "id": "ldp/collections/test-d58/documents/test-doc",
4   "type": [
5     "nif:Context",
6     "lkg:Legislation",
7     "lkg:LynxDocument"
8   ],
9   "text": "\n\n\n\n\nSecurity of Critical Infrastructure Act 2018\n\nNo. 29, 2018\n\n\n\n\nAn Act to create a
    
```

Request 2 (POST): The URL is `{{baseUrl}}/indexes/*/search`. The request body is a JSON object:

```

1 {
2   "queryString": "Federal Register of Legislation",
3   "language": "English",
4   "indexes": [
5     "test-d58"
6   ]
7 }
    
```

The response status is 200 OK, with a time of 881 ms and a size of 216.22 KB. The response body is a JSON object:

```

25   "types": [
26     "nif:OffsetBasedString",
27     "lkg:LynxDocumentPart"
28   ],
29   "title": {
30     "en": ""
31   },
32   "text": {
33     "en": "\n\n\n\n\nSecurity of Critical Infrastructure Act 2018\n\nNo. 29, 2018\n\n\n\n\nAn Act to create
    a framework for managing critical infrastructure, and for related purposes\n -\n -\n -\n -\n\nNote: An
    electronic version of this Act is available on the Federal Register of Legislation (https://www.legislation.gov.au/)\n\nContent"
34   },
    
```

For testing how the system behaves using a not existing *collectionId* while keeping the other input parameters valid (third row of Table 1), the same request made in step 3 is performed again, but this time with *collectionId=not-existing-collection*. The instance execution ends as expected with a “not existing collection” business error:

GET `{{baseUrl}}/workflows/population/instances/:populationWorkflowInstanceid` Send

Params Authorization Headers (9) Body Pre-request Script Tests Settings Coc

KEY	VALUE	DESCRIPTION	...	Bulk E
Key	Value	Description		

Path Variables

KEY	VALUE	DESCRIPTION	...	Bulk E
populationWorkflowInstanceid	940265c5-742c-11eb-aae2-0a580a01031b	(Required) The population workflow instance identi		

Body Cookies (1) Headers (8) Test Results Status: 200 OK Time: 1767 ms Size: 615 B Save Respons

Pretty Raw Preview Visualize JSON ...

```

1  {
2    "documentPlatformId": "ldp",
3    "documentId": "ldp/collections/test-d58/documents/test-doc",
4    "completed": true,
5    "completionPercentage": 100.0,
6    "errorList": [
7      {
8        "errorCode": "invalid_collection_id",
9        "errorMessage": "Provided collectionId does not exist"
10     }
11   ],
12   "collectionId": "not-existing-collection",
13   "indexId": "test-d58",
14   "tag": "my tag",
15   "completedSuccessfully": false
16 }
    
```

For testing how the system behaves using a not existing *indexId* while keeping the other input parameters valid (fourth row of Table 1), the same request made in step 3 is performed again, but this time with *indexId=not-existing-collection*. The instance execution ends as expected with a “not existing index” business error:

GET `{{baseUrl}}/workflows/population/instances/:populationWorkflowInstanceid` Send

Params Authorization Headers (9) Body Pre-request Script Tests Settings Cooki

Query Params

KEY	VALUE	DESCRIPTION	...	Bulk E
Key	Value	Description		

Path Variables

KEY	VALUE	DESCRIPTION	...	Bulk E
populationWorkflowInstanceid	8bdef5b3-8327-11eb-a7ac-0a580a011067	(Required) The population workflow instance identi		

Body Cookies (1) Headers (3) Test Results Status: 200 OK Time: 174 ms Size: 449 B Save Response

Pretty Raw Preview Visualize JSON ...

```

1  {
2    "documentPlatformId": "ldp",
3    "documentId": "ldp/collections/test-d58/documents/1111123",
4    "completed": true,
5    "completionPercentage": 100.0,
6    "errorList": [
7      {
8        "errorCode": "invalid_index_id",
9        "errorMessage": "Provided indexId does not exist"
10     }
11   ],
12   "collectionId": "test-d58",
13   "indexId": "unexisting-index-id",
    
```

For testing how the system behaves using a not existing *TimExModelId* while keeping the other input parameters valid (fifth row of Table 1), the same request made in step 3 is performed again, but this

time with *TimExModelId* = *not-existing-model-id*. The instance execution ends as expected with a “not existing enrichment model” business error:

GET `{{baseUrl}}/workflows/population/instances/:populationWorkflowInstanceId` Send

Params Authorization Headers (9) Body Pre-request Script Tests Settings Co

KEY	VALUE	DESCRIPTION	...	Bulk
Key	Value	Description		

Path Variables

KEY	VALUE	DESCRIPTION	...	Bulk
populationWorkflowInstanceId	89f1b88d-7469-11eb-aae2-0a580a01031b	(Required) The population workflow instance ident		

Body Cookies (1) Headers (8) Test Results Status: 200 OK Time: 261 ms Size: 628 B Save Respon

Pretty Raw Preview Visualize JSON ↔

```

1 {
2   "documentPlatformId": "ldp",
3   "documentId": "ldp/collections/test-d58/documents/test-doc",
4   "completed": true,
5   "completionPercentage": 100.0,
6   "errorList": [
7     {
8       "errorCode": "E01",
9       "errorMessage": "The provided enrichment models for the enrichment tasks [\"TimEx\"] do not exists."
10    }
11  ],
12  "collectionId": "test-d58",
13  "indexId": "test-d58",
14  "tag": "my tag",
15  "completedSuccessfully": false
16 }
    
```

For testing how the system behaves using an invalid Lynx document while keeping the other input parameters valid (second row of Table 1), the same request made in step 3 is performed again, but this time using an invalid Lynx document. The system correctly responds with a 400 code:

POST `{{baseUrl}}/workflows/population/instances?documentPlatform=ldp&collectionId=test-d58&indexId=unexisting-index-id&NERModi...` Send

Params Authorization Headers (12) Body Pre-request Script Tests Settings Cookie:

none form-data x-www-form-urlencoded raw binary GraphQL Text ▼

26	eli:jurisdiction	"AU"
27	eli:type_document	"Act"
28	dct:language	"not valid ISO 639 language"
29	dct:title	"Security of Critical Infrastructure Act 2018"@en

Body Cookies (1) Headers (6) Test Results Status: 400 Bad Request Time: 786 ms Size: 1.6 KB Save Response

Pretty Raw Preview Visualize JSON ↔

```

1 {
2   "status": "BAD_REQUEST",
3   "message": "The document cannot be deserialized from text/turtle format",
4   "errors": [
5     "null{\\"title\\":\\"NIF 2.1 Validation Report\\",\\"results\\":[]}{\\"title\\":\\"LYNX Data Model Validation Report\\",
6     \\"results\\":[{\\"focusNode\\":\\"ab7efec4be9f53cbcd8b8757c2f7b71\\",\\"message\\":\\"Not a value from the sh:in
7     enumeration\\",\\"path\\":\\"http://purl.org/dc/terms/language\\",\\"severity\\":\\"http://www.w3.org/ns/shacl#Violation\\",
8     \\"sourceConstraint\\":null,\\"sourceShape\\":\\"0af3ddacaa5bb19d0f8c78b5b4f1d116\\",\\"value\\":\\"not valid ISO 639
9     language\\",{\\"focusNode\\":\\"https://apis.lynx-project.eu/document-platforms/ldp/collections/test-d58/documents/
10    111123\\",\\"message\\":\\"Value does not have shape lkg:MetadataShape\\",\\"path\\":\\"http://lkg.lynx-project.eu/def/
11    metadata\\",\\"severity\\":\\"http://www.w3.org/ns/shacl#Violation\\",\\"sourceConstraint\\":null,
12    \\"sourceShape\\":\\"ba5cacdb4b9db890cca20a3897016f00\\",\\"value\\":\\"ab7efec4be9f53cbcd8b8757c2f7b71\\",
13    {\\"focusNode\\":\\"https://apis.lynx-project.eu/document-platforms/ldp/collections/test-d58/documents/111123\\",
14    \\"message\\":\\"Value does not have all the shapes in the sh:and enumeration\\",\\"path\\":null,\\"severity\\":\\"http://
15    www.w3.org/ns/shacl#Violation\\",\\"sourceConstraint\\":null,\\"sourceShape\\":\\"http://lkg.lynx-project.eu/def/
16    LegislationShape\\",\\"value\\":\\"https://apis.lynx-project.eu/document-platforms/ldp/collections/test-d58/documents/
17    111123\\"}]}"
```

2.2.3 Conclusions

All the input configurations specified in Table 1 has been tested, and the obtained results match the expected outcomes. Hence, the test can be considered passed.

2.3 TEST 3: INGESTION SPEED BENCHMARK

The objective of this test is to benchmark how fast the system is able to ingest documents, or more precisely, how fast it is able to process population workflow instances.

2.3.1 Test scenario

For this test, it is necessary to establish:

- The collection of documents: the data for which the system is benchmarked. Documents should be in the same language.
- The enrichment configuration specifies which services and models are used to enrich the documents.
- Whether the documents are indexed or not (true/false).

Then, the test consists of recording how many characters the system is able to process per unit of time (throughput), using the specified enrichment configuration. A character is considered “processed” when the population workflow instance it belongs to has successfully completed.

During the test, it is assumed that the Workflow Manager and Lynx enrichment microservices are not affected by workloads out of the context of the test.

2.3.2 Test application and results

Table 3 shows the throughput of the system measured in three different ingestion scenarios for a dataset of 198 Dutch documents. In the first scenario only entity linking was enabled. In the second and third scenarios both entity linking and translation were enabled. Moreover, in the third scenario, the translation task executor computational power was doubled with respect to the second scenario.

Enrichment configuration	Scaling configuration	Throughput (characters/second)
Entity linking: 1E260842-45A0-0001-C721-16292C0E51A0 Indexing enabled	Entity linking: x1	27708

Entity linking: 1E260842-45A0-0001-C721-16292C0E51A0	Entity linking: x1	414
Translation to English: smt-2eb02c32-1406-45a0-8974-0310becf564b	Translation: x1	
Indexing enabled		
Entity linking: 1E260842-45A0-0001-C721-16292C0E51A0	Entity linking: x1	614
Translation to English: smt-2eb02c32-1406-45a0-8974-0310becf564b	Translation: x2	
Indexing enabled		

Table 2 Throughput of the system measured in three different ingestion scenarios for the same dataset.

2.3.3 Conclusions

The results shown that, as expected, the throughput of the system highly depends on the enrichment configuration. Therefore, to forecast performance for a specific ingestion scenario, it is necessary to know which enrichment configuration will be used. Additionally, the results shown also that, the throughput of ingestions can be improved by allocating more computational power to task executors which have the slowest performance.

3 PILOT USE CASES LEVEL TESTING AND EVALUATION

This section presents the results of the tests and benchmarks that have been performed to verify the conformance of the three pilot applications with respect to their requirements. The testing methodology for the Lynx pilots has already been presented in D5.4.

3.1 CYBLY: CONTRACTS

3.1.1 Functional Testing

Functional testing is performed in automated tests during the development life cycle. For each release of a component automated unit tests based on Junit and integration test were performed. In Addition, code coverage reports were performed too, to see if main branches are covered by the tests or if additional test have to be added. For a release all tests must be passed. Currently there are 153 unit and integration test which are performed over all modules

The following is an excerpt of the generated test reports.

- Part of the JUnit (Surefire) Report of the Demo-Service which is used by the front-end application. In Total 12 Unit Tests were performed which all passed the test.

Surefire Report						
Summary						
[Summary] [Package List] [Test Cases]						
Tests	Errors	Failures	Skipped	Success Rate	Time	
12	0	0	0	100%	10.241	
Note: failures are anticipated and checked for with assertions while errors are unanticipated.						
Package List						
[Summary] [Package List] [Test Cases]						
Package	Tests	Errors	Failures	Skipped	Success Rate	Time
ai.cybly.service.lynx	6	0	0	0	100%	1.105
ai.cybly.legalnetics.nlp.regexfinder	1	0	0	0	100%	0.007
ai.cybly	3	0	0	0	100%	4.144
ai.cybly.service.legalnetics	2	0	0	0	100%	4.985

- Equivalent of the Integration Test (Failsafe) Report of the Demo. In Total 9 Integration Tests were performed which all passed the test. These tests integrate with the “real” other services. When possible for these tests were performed with Test-Containers where the services were started only for the single test. In certain cases, these tests were also performed to a dedicated test environment where the services were running. Below the excerpt of the Integration Tests for the demo service. This integration tests were performed against the Lynx services which are live.

Failsafe Report

Summary

[Summary] [Package List] [Test Cases]

Tests	Errors	Failures	Skipped	Success Rate	Time
9	0	0	2	77.778%	6.812

Note: failures are anticipated and checked for with assertions while errors are unanticipated.

Package List

[Summary] [Package List] [Test Cases]

Package	Tests	Errors	Failures	Skipped	Success Rate	Time
ai.cybyl.service.lynx	7	0	0	0	100%	6.772
ai.cybyl.service.lawthek	2	0	0	2	0%	0.04

Note: package statistics are not computed recursively, they only sum up all of its testsuites numbers.

ai.cybyl.service.lynx

	Class	Tests	Errors	Failures	Skipped	Success Rate	Time
	EntityLinkingServiceIT	1	0	0	0	100%	1.959
	NERServiceIT	1	0	0	0	100%	0.241
	TildeTranslationServiceIT	2	0	0	0	100%	2.25
	OAuthServiceIT	1	0	0	0	100%	1.698
	TimeExServiceIT	1	0	0	0	100%	0.435
	GeoLocationServiceIT	1	0	0	0	100%	0.189

- This Code Coverage Reports is also for the demo service. As it can be seen for certain packages a coverage is only by ~50%. The reason is that, standard getter and setter function and certain exception case are not tested in this module.

Lynx contract demo service

Element	Missed Instructions	Cov.	Missed Branches	Cov.	Missed Cxty	Missed Lines	Missed Methods	Missed Classes
ai.cybyl.service.lynx		46%	27 56	123 261	16 43	0 6		
ai.cybyl.service.lawthek		0%	21 27	110 124	16 22	0 3		
ai.cybyl.service.legalnetics		83%	4 26	29 96	3 23	0 3		
ai.cybyl		6%	13 19	30 37	5 11	1 3		
ai.cybyl.service.exception		n/a	11 12	18 20	11 12	1 2		
ai.cybyl.model.lawthek		n/a	15 15	21 21	15 15	3 3		
ai.cybyl.legalnetics.nlp.regexfinder.model		25%	9 31	12 61	7 29	0 4		
ai.cybyl.service.demo		0%	2 4	7 12	1 3	0 1		
ai.cybyl.model.oauth		n/a	6 17	6 25	6 17	0 1		
ai.cybyl.legalnetics.nlp.regexfinder		80%	3 10	3 34	1 5	0 1		
ai.cybyl.controller		n/a	1 2	1 4	1 2	0 1		
Total	1,296 of 2,557	49%	47 of 74	36%	112 219	360 695	82 182	5 28

Created with JaCoCo 0.8.6.202009150832

3.1.2 Data and Database Integrity Testing

Data Integrity tests are performed within the functional testing.

There are 2 types of this tests:

- Document Conversion: These tests test if different document formats are correctly converted to Lynx documents

Test Cases		
[Summary] [Package List] [Test Cases]		
DocumentControllerTest		
	convert_2_successful	2.307
	convert_successful	0.14
DocumentServiceTest		
	convert_pdf_2	0.223
	convert_msg_single_attachment	0.252
	convert_msg_two_attachments	0.784
	convert_eml_mail_attachments	0.576
	convert_eml	0.051
	convert_msg	0.053
	convert_pdf	0.084
	convert_eml_single_attachment	0.215
	convert_msg_mail_attachments	0.245
	convert_eml_comb_attachments	0.826
	convert_eml_two_attachments	0.391
	convert_docx	0.096

- Lynx Document Persistent: reference Lynx documents are imported to the Pilot Platform and then automatic checks are performed if all metadata parts are stored correctly within the pilot system

DocumentServiceTest		
	addDocument_minimalDocument()	0.423
	addDocument_missingMetadata_language	0.252
	addDocument_missingMetadata	0.184
	addDocument_missingContext	0.276
	addDocument_missingId	0.256
	addDocument_missingType	0.054
	addDocument_missingText	0.088
	addDocument_invalidJson	0.252
	addDocument_withParts	0.645
	addDocument_withParts_Preamble	1.226
	addDocument_withParts_MultipleTitle	1.152
	addDocument_withSubParts	1.269
	addDocument_withParts_missingId	0.245
	addDocument_withAnnotations	1.843
	deleteDocument	0.698

3.1.3 User Interface Testing

User Interface testing has been performed manually based on scripts to see if all the necessary functionality is available. Below an excerpt of the different test performed and the steps to perform these tests.

Test Summary	Priority	Execution Status	OrderId	Step	Test Data	Expected Result	Step Result
Setup a organisation for a new user	Major / Should have	UNEXECUTED	1	Add Organisation	Create a new organisation in the BO & assign an user as Administrator	Organisation is created	PASS
			2	Login is Administrator	Login is as the user which has been assigned as administrator and go to settings / organisations	The newly added organisation is available	PASS
Login	Major / Should have	PASS	1	Login	Login with a previously registered user where the userId is all lower case	Login possible	PASS
			2	Logout	null	User is logged out	PASS
			3	Login	Login in again with this user, but this time write the userId all in capital letters	Login possible	PASS
Forgott password	Major / Should have	PASS	1	Press the forgott password link	Provide e-mail address to request resetting password	An confirmation is send, and there must be an e-mail in the inbox with a link to reset password	PASS
			2	Login	Login as the user with the old password	Login possible	PASS
			3	Logout	null	User is logged out	PASS
			4	Reset password	Follow the link in the e-mail and reset the password	Password has changed	PASS
			5	Logout	null	User is logged out	PASS
			6	Login with old password	old password	Login is not possible	PASS
			7	Login with new password	new password	Login is possible	PASS
Bookmark a document	Major / Should have	PASS	1	Bookmark document	Search for a document and add it to an existing folder	document is added to the folder	PASS
			2	Bookmark document, new folder	Bookmark the same document but this time select "create folder and add"	new folder is created and document is added to the folder	PASS
Bookmark a search	Major / Should have	PASS	1	bookmark search	perform a search and bookmark the search	search query is bookmarked and visible as a kind of sub-folder in the folder where the bookmark has been added	PASS
Create a folder	Major / Should have	PASS	1	create folder	go to personal folders and create a new folder, fill only required fields	new folder is created	PASS
Rename a folder	Major / Should have	PASS	1	Rename folder	Open a folder in the edit mode and change the name of the folder and save the change	Folder name is updated and the folder list is updated too. New folder name is shown	PASS
Move a folder	Major / Should have	PASS	1	Move folder to top	open the detail of a folder and change the parent folder to no parent folder	folder is in the top view of the personal folders	PASS
			2	Move folder to sub-folder	open the detail of a folder and change the parent folder any existing folder	folder is now a sub- folder of the chosen folder, a dialog is shown that the folder will have the access rights from the parent folder	PASS
Move a folder to an organisation	Major / Should have	PASS	1	move folder	go to folder detail view in private context, create a folder and move the folder to the organization	the folder is no longer in the privat personal context	PASS
			2	switch to organization context	switch to the context of the organization the folder has been moved to	user in the context of the organization	PASS
			3	check if folder is there	go to personal folder	the moved folder is now listed within personal folders of the organization	PASS
Reset Password	Major / Should have	PASS	1	precondition: user is not logged in Go to homepage -> login-in -> forgot password		dialog where user can enter password is shown	PASS
			2	provide email address and request to reset password		confirmation dialog is shown and a reset password email is received	PASS
			3	confirm link in reset password email		a dialog is shown where the user can enter the new password	PASS
			4	provide new password twice and store		confirmation dialog is presented	PASS
			5	confirm dialog		user is logged in dashboard is shown	PASS

In the current stage of the product there is no automated Selenium test, as the product is still changing based on customer needs.

In addition, the UI have been compared to the original screen design and either the screens have been adapted accordantly or the difference have been accepted.

3.1.4 Security and Access Control Testing

These tests were part of the UI tests and automated functional tests.

3.1.5 Performance Testing

To test the performance of the system, 5 different documents were subjected to a conversion process and afterwards an annotation process. The following annotations were performed in combination: GEO, NER, TimeEx, Regular Expressions, Entity Linking.

	Time to convert to a Lynx Document	Time to annotate the document	Number of annotations found
Short PDF (2 pages) without OCR	1,401s	0,2s	58

Short PDF (2 pages) with OCR	1,612s	0,2s	58
Long PDF (28 pages) without OCR	45s	4s	798
Long PDF (28 pages) with OCR	2m 38s	4s	798
Word document (8 pages)	0,989s	2,6s	110

It can be summarised that the throughput of a single document depends less on the time for annotating and more on the time for converting the document into a Lynx document. Here specifically it is the time for the OCR process that takes the most time.

3.1.6 Benchmarks and competency questions

In addition to the functional tests, this section asks a selection of competency questions to test the benefit to the end user.

Competency question	Test	Comment
Annotations are complete and correct.	10 hand-picked documents were automatically annotated and checked.	GEO annotation could be more finely granulated ² . Time annotation tends to interpret 4-digit numbers as year if <= 20xx. ³
Extracted text in the documents is equal to the text from the document. Order of the text from top to bottom is respected.	10 hand-picked documents were automatically converted	The comparison showed that for some scanned documents where the external scan process already creates a text layer, this order is not applied. Special characters are sometimes reproduced incorrectly by the OCR process, which leads to poorer quality in the annotation, e.g. "B" instead of "ß". ⁴
Documents can be found on the basis of various criteria	Approx. 1000 documents which are already grouped were loaded into the system and checked whether the	The search found more documents, but the searched

² Currently, optimisations with NER are still taking place to achieve this granularity.

³ There is a post-processing using domain know-how which removes the wrong annotations, e.g. it is unlikely that there are years smaller than 19xx in contracts.

⁴ Optimisation of the OCR process is outside the scope of the project, but will certainly have to be looked at more closely in the course of further commercialisation. For the pilot, an open source solution was used that may have to be replaced by a commercial solution.

	documents belonging together can also be found on the basis of various criteria, e.g. a combination of terms.	documents were always in the top results.
It should be possible to find documents with certain clauses.	Documents containing the relevant clauses were selected manually and a search was carried out to check whether this was possible.	Passed

In summary, it can be said that the system meets the requirements, but needs adaptation / optimisation for the individual use cases of Cyblys customers.

3.2 CUATRECASAS: LABOUR LAW

Cuatrecasas performed this testing based on functional and non-functional testing described on the testing document 5.3 and on the requirements document. The testing was run on the week of March 1st for all the results displayed below.

3.2.1 Data and Database Integrity Testing

Test Id	Description	Outcome
1	Users are stored in App Database	Passed
2	Company related with users and collections are stored in App Database	Passed
3	Personal settings from a user is stored in App Database	Passed
4	Question history by user is stored in App Database	Passed
5	User role is properly stored in App Database	Passed
6	Audit log stored in App Database	Passed
7	History activity stored in App Database	Passed

3.2.2 Function Testing

Test Id	Id & Module	Description	Outcome	REQUIREMENT
---------	-------------	-------------	---------	-------------

1	UPLOAD	The user uploads a document into the LKG. This is in PDF format in Spanish into one private collection. the classification will be Spanish jurisdiction, title the name of the law.	Passed	REQ07
2	QUESTION	The user writes a legal question selecting EN language and Spanish and Austrian jurisdiction and retrieving the answers in Spanish for both jurisdictions	Passed	REQ06
3	USER PROFILE	The user will be able to select (1 to N) jurisdictions/countries to ask/work with (from the available jurisdictions for this project).	Passed	REQ02
4	FAVOURITES	The user searches documents in a collection and select a subset of documents from a private collection and create a Favourite	Passed	REQ06
5	USER PROFILE	The user must save personal settings, which should be default when they use the application. Select default language (for answers), default jurisdiction and default documents and Collections.	Passed	REQ04
6	COMPANY SETTINGS	The user must go to Company Settings and see Private and Public collections that was allowed to use for questions.	Passed	REQ05
7	FAVOURITES	The user must be able to edit their favourites: select (add or remove) their “subset of the Legal Knowledge Graph” to do their search/question-answer.	Passed	REQ06
8	FAVOURITES	The user must be able to edit their favourites: select (add or remove) their “subset of the Legal Knowledge Graph” to do their search/question-answer.	Passed	REQ06
9	FAVOURITES	Metadata search. The user will filter the collections selected by Type of Document (“Law” by default), Country/Jurisdiction, Company (*), Sub-type of Law, Legal Domain/Specialisation (“Labour” by default).	Passed	REQ06
10	ANSWERS	The question retrieves answers from the selected favourites grouped by document from the LKG	Passed	REQ08

11	ANSWERS	Each answer must have a link to the full document, to the paragraph and to the translated paragraph	Passed	REQ08
12	ANSWERS	Rate answers	Passed	REQ14
13	ANSWERS	Display the score and the relevance must be by the score - The most accurate answer on top	Passed	REQ08
14	TRANSLATION	Select ES language once we do the question and on user profile select EN as a default on answers. Answers should appear in EN in any jurisdiction	Passed	REQ10
15	QUESTION HISTORY	After sending several questions, go this functionality and select one of the questions done. The system will display the same answers.	Passed	REQ12
16	LOGIN	Use an external Cuatrecasas account with access to the system and log in	Passed	REQ17
17	LOGIN	Use an internal Cuatrecasas account with access to the system and SSO must be applied	Passed	REQ17

Lynx CGP API:

Lynx CGP API No Environment, 2 mins ago

RUN SUMMARY

	1	2	3	4	5
▶ GET Info (Ok)	5	0			
▶ GET Info (BadRequest)	5	0			
▶ GET Info (DomainException)	5	0			
▶ GET Info (Exception)	5	0			
▶ POST Create Company	5	0			
▶ GET Get Company	5	0			
▶ POST Create Transform	5	0			
▶ GET Get Transform Types	5	0			
▶ GET DM Get Document	5	0			
▶ GET DM Get Documents (ALL)	5	0			
▶ GET WM Get Document	5	0			
▶ GET WM Get Documents (ALL)	5	0			
▶ GET Jurisdictions	5	0			
▶ GET Language	5	0			
▶ GET DocType	5	0			
▶ GET DocContext	5	0			
▶ GET Create Workflow	5	0			

Accuracy testing:

In order to test Lynx services in the context of Cuatrecasas Pilot, an experiment has been performed to evaluate the accuracy of the retrieved documents.

The experiment consisted in the evaluation of the document retrieved from the UPM Lynx portal given a natural language query. The experiment uses the question answering dataset created by Cuatrecasas which is described in Deliverable 5.7.

The dataset contains 150 questions in natural language (in Spanish language) and each question is related with the title of the article which contains the correct answer. The Articles correspond to the different articles in which the Spanish Worker's Statute is divided. Each article has been uploaded as a LynxDocument in the LKG in a separate Collection for the experiment

The evaluation is performed by checking the 10 best results retrieved by the Lynx Portal for each question. If the target article of the question is retrieved the first one, the result is classified as Perfect. If the target article is between the first 4 ones the result is classified as correct and if it is in any other part of the retrieved ones the result is classified as 'rest'. Target articles not retrieved in the list of 10 are marked as 'not found'.

The results of the experiment are: 61 Perfect (40%), 47 Correct (31%), 21 rest (14%) and 20 not found (13%). Results show a good accuracy reflected in the Perfect and Correct groups. Further parallel UPM experiments have been executed over the query to preprocess it before it is executed over the Lynx Portal. This preprocess consisted in extracting the terms that are in the query and increasing their value in the search process. This preprocessing has increased the results up to 67 Perfect queries and 49 correct queries, reducing the number of 'rest' up to only 13 queries.

The preprocessing task is not fully integrated in the normal search service of the Lynx Platform because it has to be evaluated in more complex scenarios.

Results obtained using the default configuration of the Lynx Portal:

3.2.3 User Interface Testing

Test Id	Description	Outcome	Comment
1	UX: Verify ease of navigation	Passed	
2	Verify GUI standards and Cuatrecasas branding requirements	Passed	We use a Cuatrecasas development template on which we ensure: branding, responsive and security. Validation must be also at development level

Capture of the CC user interface for query and document search:

3.2.4 Performance Testing

Test Id	Description	Outcome
1	Verify response time to access the system	Passed
2	Verify response time to upload a new document with split	Passed
3	Verify response time to present the list of answers by jurisdiction	Passed

4	verify response time to on-demand translation of results (paragraph, article...)	Passed
5	Performance evaluation and data collection response time	Passed

Communication workflow to upload a new document with split (response time: 12.325ms)

Communication workflow to search a document (response time 7.948 ms):

Communication workflow to answer and translate (response time 5.826 ms):

Response time CGP API with lynx system:

▶ GET	http://localhost:58568/api/server/infoOk	200	12 ms
▶ GET	http://localhost:58568/api/server/InfoBadRequest	200	8 ms
▶ GET	http://localhost:58568/api/server/InfoDomainException	200	1308 ms
▶ GET	http://localhost:58568/api/server/InfoException	200	200 ms
▶ POST	http://localhost:58568/api/Company	200	307 ms
▶ GET	http://localhost:58568/api/Company/	200	99 ms
▶ POST	http://localhost:58568/api/transform/create	200	2.44 s
▶ GET	http://localhost:58568/api/transform/Types	200	16 ms
▶ GET	http://localhost:58568/api/workflow/cuatrecasas-public-dev/Documents/0326c0e2	200	1810 ms
▶ GET	http://localhost:58568/api/collection/cuatrecasas-public-dev/Documents	200	146 ms
▶ GET	http://localhost:58568/api/collection/cuatrecasas-public-dev/Documents/0326c0e2	200	1583 ms
▶ GET	http://localhost:58568/api/collection/cuatrecasas-public-dev/Documents	200	147 ms
▶ GET	http://localhost:58568/api/lookup/Jurisdiction/	200	50 ms
▶ GET	http://localhost:58568/api/lookup/Language/	200	51 ms
▶ GET	http://localhost:58568/api/lookup/DocType/	200	49 ms
▶ GET	http://localhost:58568/api/lookup/DocContext/	200	51 ms
▶ GET	https://alp-api-88-staging.cloud.itandtel.at/api/workflows/LKGP?collectionId=Lynx_CC_0c03c926-8ac5-4be2-b75a-1188ae1d5383_Development&indexDocument=true&DMIImplementation=UPM	200	313 ms

3.2.5 Security and Access Control Testing

Test Id	Id & Module	Description	Outcome	REQUIREMENT
1	LOGIN	Use an external Cuatrecasas account with access to the system and log in	Passed	REQ17
2	LOGIN	Use an internal Cuatrecasas account with access to the system and SSO must be applied	Passed	REQ17

3	USER ADMIN	Create a new external user with access to two private collections and one public collection. Login with this external account and go to Company Settings and verify there are these collections on the list	Passed	
4	LOGIN	Forgot password for an external user and get new password	Passed	

3.3 DNV GL: GEOTHERMAL ENERGY

This chapter section covers the test results of the GTE demonstrator based on the test plan as laid out D5.4.

3.3.1 Data and Database Integrity Testing

In order to guarantee the integrity of the database and the results shown to the user we have deployed an additional indexer endpoint that is guaranteed to be strictly synchronized with the relevant collection in the document manager. This way the output results are guaranteed to be complete.

3.3.2 Function Testing

The Functional test described in this paragraph was done in the GTE demonstrator version in early March 2021. Most tests can be reproduced or verified by comparing with the pilot demonstration during the webinar 2 on Jan 11 2021⁵

In the table below, the test results are presented including comments on causes or potential fixes. Test were executed in week 9 2021 when the demonstrator was hosted at itandtel.at which was in use until March 15 20201. As from that date the demonstrator was migrated to a new server (visit <https://lynx-project.eu/> to learn about accessing the demonstrator)

Test description	Outcome	Comment
Analyse a single file: user uploads / drag-drops one PDF	Passed	
Visualize single document with annotations	Passed	
Annotations have the correct colour to indicate a category	Passed	Incorrect colour indication can be updated in Poolparty and are displayed after reprocessing
Semantic search results are presenter in the 'recommender page' per category	Passed	
Search results show a 'fingerprint' of terms to indicate it relevancy	Passed	

¹ ⁵ Lynx Webinar #2.2: Geothermal Energy use case - 3 Business Cases on top of the Lynx LKG <https://youtu.be/MeyoWqmkkPY>

User can navigate through categories of search results without losing the data	Passed	
User can use global search within the data space (without the file drop-zone)	Passed	This is done in the search section using 'keyword' based search

3.3.3 Benchmarks and competency questions

In addition to the functional testing, in this section a selection of competency questions are benchmarked in order to test the use to the end user.

Competency question	Test	Comment
Recommender presents permit applications close to the geographical proximity of the user input document	5 handpicked documents, not stored in the DCM where tested. Geonames were highlighted correctly and correctly matched to a recommended permit document	Test was successful. Nevertheless, granularity can be fine-tuned e.g. starting on city / municipality level and exclude country level. And there is limited disambiguation: e.g. 'well' is tagged as a geothermal facility element' in the sentence '... well positioned', where it was intended as an expression of 'good'.

Recommender highlights relevant domain specific terminologies

10 handpicked documents, not in the DCM where tested.

Cross checked 2-3 concepts for each scheme in the color legend. They were all presented correctly.

Recommended permit excerpt is translated correctly.

4 handpicked permit related documents (in Dutch) where tested. Permits presented in the recommender are enriched with a translated excerpt

Translated excerpts are checked by native speakers and deemed acceptable

The screenshot shows a document titled 'Beleidsnotitie zonneparken en kleine windmolens Gemeente Westerwolde'. It includes the issuer 'Westerwolde' and the date '2019-04-25'. A table lists related entities: Netherlands, Groningen, and Gemeente Vlagtwedde. A 'Translation NL-EN indicator' (NL-EN) is present. A 'Source document' is also indicated. The document content includes a section titled '1. Beleidsnotitie zonneparken en kleine windmolens' with a sub-section 'Energie in het landschap'. A 'Translated excerpt in recommender' is shown at the bottom left, containing the text: '1. Solar parks and small wind turbines policy note Energy in the landscape The policy note on solar parks and small wind turbines is complementary to the "Western wolde together" fish paper and develops energy in the landscape in Westerwolde over the next five years (2019-2024). Involving residents...'. The document content also includes: 'De beleidsnotitie zonneparken en kleine windmolens is een aanvullende uitwerking op visiedocument "Westerwolde samen verduurzamen" en geeft een uitwerking aan energie in het landschap in Westerwolde voor de komende vijf jaar (2019-2024). Het betrekken van inwoners bij de beleidskeuzes is een belangrijk onderdeel in het proces geweest. Er zijn drie'.

3.3.4 User Interface Testing

Test description	Outcome	Comment
Verify ease of navigation through the set of screens.	Passed. The UI is intuitive and guidance is given to the user where needed	
Verify sample screens conform to GUI standards.	Passed.	Standard REACT components are used in order to comply to GUI standards
The System shall be easy-to-use and shall be appropriate for the target market.	Passed	The principle of the chosen system design is easy to use and appropriate for the target market.

3.3.5 Performance Testing

Test description	Outcome	Comment
Verify response time to access the system.	Passed	Load time is 564 ms. (Ideally a site loads in 1-2 sec)
Verify response time to analyses a single PDF document (approximately 15 pages ~ 1 mb)	Fail	This is a known point of improvement and can be solves by adding resources. Current performance is 42 sec for a 15 page PDF document which is quite poor. We estimate a performance <10 sec would be more acceptable.

3.3.6 Security and Access Control Testing

Test description	Outcome	Comment
Verify security through username and password mechanisms.	Passed	Access credentials are required to access the demonstrator
Verify functional security based on user role	Not tested	As the demonstrator only has one user role, verifying user-based security was not tested.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The results from integration tests of the Lynx platform presented in Section 2 showed that the Lynx platform microservices are correctly integrated. Moreover, the results showed that the rate at which the system is able to ingest documents strongly depends on the decided enrichment configuration, and that the speed of ingestion can be increased by allocating more computational power to task executors which have the slowest performance.

Section 3 presented the results of the tests and benchmarks that have been performed to verify the conformance of the three pilot applications with respect to their requirements. The results showed that the three pilot applications are correctly integrated with the Lynx platform, and that the software is conformant with the requirements, with only some minor performance problems in the case of the Geothermal Energy pilot.

5 BIBLIOGRAPHY

- [1] F. Maganza, J. Moreno-Schneider, P. Boil, P. Verhoeven, C. Sageder and T. Test , “D5.4 Testing and Evaluation Plan,” 2020.
- [2] J. Moreno-Schneider, G. Rehm, F. Maganza, S. Karampatakis and V. Rodríguez Doncel, “D4.5 Final implementation and report of Data and Content Curation Services,” 2021.